

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Resin Infusion Composites for Aerospace

Michael Edwards, Boeing Research & Technology Australia

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

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Introduction

- Boeing Australia manufacturing for over 90 years
- *Yesterday*: Resin Infusion (RI) Composites
 - Fundamentals
 - Key benefits
 - Current aerospace applications
- *Today*: Boeing Aerostructures Australia – Dreamliner 787 Moveable Trailing Edges
- *Tomorrow*: Future opportunities for RI Composites

Boeing Aerostructures Australia

- Australia's major aerostructures company
- A wholly owned Boeing subsidiary
- Operating in Australia for over 90 years
- One site: Fishermans Bend, Melbourne
- Design, manufacture, testing and certification of structural airframe components

Centre of Excellence for Edges and RI Composites for Boeing Commercial Airplanes

Resin Infusion

- **What is Resin Infusion?**
 - Control combining **resin** and **dry fibre reinforcements** on lay-up mandrel
 - A Boeing Patented out of autoclave process
 - Controlled Atmospheric Pressure Resin Infusion (CAPRI)
- **Why Resin Infusion?**
 - Simple standardised process
 - Lower material costs
 - Higher deposition rates
 - No debulking
 - High drapeability
 - Net shape moulded parts
 - No surface films required
 - Reduced need for freezers
 - Lower capital costs (ovens vs autoclaves)

Controlled Atmospheric Pressure Resin Infusion (CAPRI)

High Rate Layup

High Quality Parts

Resin Infusion – Key Benefits

- **Value proposition**
 - Lower material costs
 - Higher deposition rates
 - Simplicity of forming
 - Lower capital (ovens vs autoclaves)
 - Local supply chain
- **Rate Enabling**
 - High material lay-down rates (no debulking)
 - Co-curing of integrated parts
- **Lean Engineering**
 - Long shop life for reinforcement (18+ months)
 - Right sized production systems (ovens)
 - High quality parts (low defect rates)

Non Autoclave Production System

Australian Designed Ovens and Production System

High Quality Parts (900+ s/s)

BAA 787 Outboard Flap

Key Resin Infusion Aerospace Applications

1990

2020

Boeing

NASA Stitched Wing

Boeing

C-17 MLG

Boeing

787 MTE

Premium
Aerotech

A400M Rear Cargo Door

Boeing

Stiffened Architectures

Premium
Aerotech

787 Aft Pressure Bulkhead

Mitsubishi

MRJ Empennage

Bombardier

C-Series Wing

AeroComposite

MS21 Wing

Customers and products

Boeing 787 Dreamliner

787 Inboard Flap

787 Flaperon

787 Outboard Flap

787 Aileron

BAA work statement: process development, design, build, through life support

Future opportunities for RI Composites

- Next Commercial Airplane Programs
 - Highly integrated structures
 - Complex architectures
 - High lay down rates
 - Reduced parts count
 - Automated fabrication and assembly options
 - Low infrastructure costs (NRE)
 - Highly leveraged MBE approaches
- Longer Term Development Focus
 - Toughened functionalized material systems
 - Ultra-high fabrication rates
 - Large acreage complex architectures
 - Low cost primary structure applications

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